

At: Workshop “Exploring Porto in Cholera Contexts: Multidisciplinary Approaches”, an initiative developed within the framework of the project *BeFrail – Porto in Times of Cholera and War: A Bioarchaeological Approach to Human Frailty*, 12.01.2024, Porto, Portugal.

The Contribution of Research in Archives and Documentary Sources

- Alexandra Esteves (Universidade do Minho)
- Rui Leandro Maia (Universidade Fernando Pessoa)
- Célia Oliveira (Universidade do Minho)

BeFRail - Porto in Times of Cholera and War: A Bioarchaeological Approach to Human Frailty. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02398.PTDC>.

Title: The contribution of research in archives and documentary sources

Alexandra ESTEVES^{1,2}, Rui Leandro MAIA^{3,4}, Célia OLIVEIRA^{1,2}

1 Lab2PT – Laboratory of Landscapes, Heritage and Territory (University of Minho, Braga, Portugal)

2 IN2PAST – Associate Laboratory for Research and Innovation in Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory (University of Évora, Portugal)

3 University Fernando Pessoa, Porto, Portugal

4 CITCEM – Transdisciplinary Research Center for Culture, Space and Memory, University of Porto, Portugal

Abstract: Archives are institutions whose mission is to preserve, process, and provide access to a wide range of sources (written, iconographic, material, and oral) originating from the past and representing the collective memory of a community, region, and/or country. In historical research, archives play a crucial role, as the consultation and analysis of available sources enable historians to interpret and gain a deeper understanding of the events, cultures, and societies that have shaped the world in which we live.

This presentation aims to examine the resources that archives make available to historians seeking to study human vulnerability in the past. Taking as its starting point

the doctoral research project “Human Vulnerability in Written Sources: Exploring Sociobiological Determinants in the City of Porto during the Nineteenth Century (1832–1899)”, the presentation will analyse the sources underpinning the project, their characteristics, and their potential contributions to its successful implementation.

Keywords: Archive; Sources; Historical Research; Human Vulnerability; Porto.